

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

A conversation on Federated Learning

Federated Learning is the backbone of GenoMed4All's Artificial Intelligence framework for hematological diseases, and an emerging technology for the healthcare realm.

What is it exactly? Why does it matter? How does it work? – if any of these questions pique your interest, you are in the right place! Let us explore the ins and outs of Federated Learning and unravel its potential for healthcare in this two-part miniseries.

What is Federated Learning?

Federated Learning is the latest piece in the ever-growing puzzle of machine data concepts and the underlying patterns that bind them together... and thus, a fundamental step in the evolution of how we look at and understand data. Throughout this journey, each milestone reached becomes a sort of 'breakpoint' in the continuum of change, a new push forward driven by the combined forces of emerging research outcomes, technological prowess and business needs colliding at a particular moment in time. These communities –research, technology and business– are converging, and this massive shift creates new and exciting opportunities for Federated Learning to bloom.

The continuum of machine data evolution

The idea of **data warehouses** as a technology first appeared in the 80s and continued to reign supreme through the 90s as the go-to data architecture for large enterprises. The reason? It offers

a way for them to integrate all analytics data into a single central repository, where they can then be optimally accessed, queried and visualized as a whole [1]. Data warehouses kicked off the conversation on data governance and continue to be relevant nowadays. However, they are not a one-size-fits-all solution, requiring highly structured data and usually running on third parties' proprietary hardware.

Then Hadoop shows up and changes everything. Thanks to the Map-Reduce paradigm [2], companies have free access to an open source solution that can process raw data –either unstructured or semi-structured– in a way that data warehouses cannot... and the emerging **cloud computing** technology promises to free them from the shackles of on-premise infrastructure. With all this data suddenly there for the taking, the focus shifts to finding a better way to collect it and store it: the so-called **data lake**.

The number of connected devices has skyrocketed and so has the amount of raw data available. The **Internet of Everything** (IoE) has taken off and it has become painfully clear that cloud computing cannot keep up the pace in this new paradigm of ever-growing data: slow speeds, bandwidth issues and a deficient approach towards data privacy and security are the fuel to the flames of a new, brighter fire: **edge computing** [3]. This new era ushers in a shift in computing power: from a central node in the cloud to (unsurprisingly) the "edges" of the network –closer to the data sources–, where small-scale storage and data processing can be performed locally.

Problem solved, right? Well, not really. For years, we have tirelessly gone through every trick in the book on processor chip design to try and keep up with Moore's law, but engineers seem to have reached the limit in terms of transistor scale and capacity. In this race, traditional general-purpose processors chips –what we normally call CPUs (Central Processing Units)– have given way to specialized **accelerators** [4] –like GPUs (Graphical Processing Units) and TPUs (Tensor Processing Units)– capable of handling dedicated AI/ML workloads and performing much better under specific size, weight and/or power constraints.

In the highly distributed modern world of Big Data, a centralized approach is not going to cut it anymore; especially in domains –healthcare, finance...– that require a massive volume of distributed, sensitive data to train algorithms. Data is everywhere and the idea of accessing, processing and consuming it from a single central place seems lacking. How to scale up then? Let's move on to the next frontier: **federation** [5].

A federated –or decentralized– query processing system reconciles the need to access data in a unified way with the inherent nature of the data itself: heterogeneous and distributed. These query engines have no control over the datasets and data providers are free to come and go in a federated scheme. Together with improved flexibility, this also introduces an additional level of performance complexity –mostly related to data fragmentation, disparities in access and processing power– that centralized systems are typically exempt from.

The final leap from here to Federated Learning is once again motivated by the ebbs and flows of business –the juxtaposition of the prevalence of AI models and the supremacy of data, versus the need for numerical and resource frugality, and the real, often bitter implications on both privacy and ethics.

Reflecting on our journey through the research, technological and business dimensions, we can see that Federated Learning is indeed part of an evolution of machine data concepts and patterns that has been going on for quite some time. As such, every single one of these milestones we have briefly touched upon along the way –the ‘breakpoints’ in this continuum– emerged as a result of mixing new, exciting research outcomes with a keen ambition to address pressing business needs at the time.

All in all, Federated Learning is here to stay... let's see what it has to offer.

Federated Learning: an overview

Unlike standard Machine Learning approaches, the revolution in Federated Learning starts by bringing model to data, instead of the other way around. The concept is surprisingly simple: let us train a model in multiple decentralized edge nodes. Each holds their local dataset, and none of them will be exchanging data. Following this approach, a community will be able to create and share a global AI/ML model without centralizing the data in a single location.

As any other technology, Federated Learning comes with its own peculiarities. At the forefront of these, we find a **decentralized learning process** over multiple clients interconnected in a network, which generates information exchange on model and framework control data exclusively. Moreover, training datasets do not leave the edge nodes. Consequently, the model is trained locally and able to preserve data privacy. Every new training process is orchestrated in the same manner: first, we initialize the global model and broadcast it to the edge nodes in our network; next we monitor each and every one of our training phases and finally, we aggregate the result before deployment.

Federated Learning comes in different flavors [6]. The most common one is the so-called **model-centric** approach, in which training is carried out at the edge nodes and a central model is updated

through a federation. As an umbrella term, this approach applies to two additional subtypes: cross-device and cross-silo.

The **cross-device** alternative is based on horizontal data sharing: training is carried out in a large distributed network of multiple smart devices –as is the case for Google and Android– and thus, should carefully consider the capabilities at the edge in terms of connectivity, limited computing and battery life.

In contrast, the **cross-silo** subtype relies instead on vertical data sharing: organizations (e.g. hospitals, private companies...) or data centers take on the role of edge nodes and share incentives to train a common model, while adhering to strict data security standards and refraining from peer-to-peer data sharing.

Another flavor in this "FL menu" is the **data-centric** approach [6], a peer-to-peer distributed learning formula through which each node in the network graph sends and receives gradient steps from its neighbors in order to reach global model convergence via gradual consensus.

And what about GenoMed4All? Considering everything we have told you so far, our project falls neatly into the cross-silo category of Federated Learning, though there is always room for a potential exploration on how to reach a clinical consensus on horizontal data sharing. After all, any and all advances on rare diseases strongly rely on both collaboration and standardization efforts. That said, and for the sake of clarity, from this point onwards we will focus our attention on the cross-silo approach exclusively.

Why Federated Learning?

An attractive new concept for healthcare informatics

It is no secret that systems and processes in the healthcare realm are, more often than not, extremely complex. This complexity directly contributes to a high level of **fragmentation** that mostly stems from the **sensitive nature** of healthcare data. Consequently, countless regulations have been developed to dictate the way we access and analyze this kind of data, which typically falls under what is called Protected Health Information (PHI). At their core, these regulatory efforts share the same ambition: ensure that sensitive patient data stays either within local institutions (clinical sites, hospitals) or with the individuals themselves, effectively protecting patient privacy.

In light of all this, the value proposition of Federated Learning in healthcare boils down to two critical features: **scalability** and **data protection** [7].

First up, Federated Learning streamlines the scaling up process for training ML models in multiple edge nodes –think hospitals, clinical sites, research institutions in GenoMed4All– which can theoretically improve the performance of the predictive models, reducing selection bias and facilitating the onboarding of new data providers and sources to the whole training strategy. We are also talking about a framework with built-in re-training and expansion capabilities by design, which greatly simplifies reusability of predictive algorithms.

Similarly, and as far as data protection goes, Federated Learning is a perfect fit for the healthcare domain [8] since data is not required to leave the clinical data provider's premises at any point. This has huge implications in a clinical setting and may be key in navigating the current limitations imposed by data protection laws on highly sensitive data –like PHI, for example–, since technically there is no data sharing involved. Coincidentally, this also solves the fragmentation issue by effectively linking multiple health data sources for the purpose of training predictive models.

All in all, Federated Learning seems to check all the boxes in healthcare sector wishlist, but real-world applications are still few and hard to come by. According to Gartner (and as of 2021), Federated Learning is in the middle of a climb up the initial slope of the Privacy Hype Cycle, which effectively labels it as an '**innovation trigger**' in the digital ethics landscape: a technology in its early stages with some proof-of-concept stories to share and lots of media attention, but with no proven commercial viability yet.

So, what exactly is holding us back? It's time to address the still untapped potential of Federated Learning.

How to build a Federated Learning framework?

The challenges ahead

At first glance, we might be quick to assume that a cross-silo approach for Federated Learning seems to be the easiest path to take implementation-wise: after all, we are dealing with a limited number of well-known, addressable edge systems, which are more powerful and reliable overall. However, this apparent 'simplicity' conceals another wide spectrum of issues to account for, either from a **business**, **data integration**, **security** or **platform** perspective. Let's dive right in.

Business challenges

In a Federated Learning network, there is a risk that edge nodes may behave 'selfishly' in order to compromise between model accuracy and cost [9]. This delicate balance of risk-reward is intimately tied to the governance of the network itself and has many implications on what is

commonly known as 'health justice'. In the context of GenoMed4All, this theme crystalizes into how we define and enforce 'equity' among nodes in the network and our capability to properly adjust for discrepancies in overall performance and model accuracy when onboarding a 'dissonant' node. Anticipating these 'dissonances' in an FL network is key, since participants may not be evenly matched in terms of the resources –human and material alike– they are able to commit to this joint enterprise.

On this point, the research community has already dedicated quite a lot of effort to find out how we can maximize benefit for each node with limited engagement: the answer seems to lie in the way we estimate both the motivation and contribution of our network nodes.

On the topic of **motivation**, we may ask ourselves: *how do I reward participation for each edge node in a way that ensures that the central server can maintain optimal quality?* Putting in place incentive mechanisms that work for all participants involved is key, especially in such a highly heterogenous environment. These incentives or rewards may take multiple forms, like accessing specific central services, benefitting from models without contributing to their training, the opportunity to launch a new training plan... you name it. For the estimation of a node's **contribution**, however, a reward can only be fixed if the 'value' each node brings to the network can be adequately quantified, and this is not a straightforward exercise: it has to consider both dataset size and quality, and the computation needs to then be correlated to the accuracy of the final model and updated with each training iteration [10].

Data integration challenges

When considering **data usage**, we must be mindful of how to onboard organizations operating across multiple geographic, political and regulatory scenarios –especially those dictating data protection regulations– to this FL network.

The first barrier we must be aware of in terms of data integration is the **minimum anonymized dataset** that needs to be shared for the initial FL model to be correctly tested, developed and bootstrapped. Another significant roadblock are the **access policies** that govern dataset extraction at the edge and define what is and is not allowed in terms of data science operations on metadata and model alike. As of today, there is a marked interest on how to strike the right integration between authorization policy language to encode these access policies and the technology required to enforce them.

Additionally, there is the ever-present matter of **data quality**, which the distributed nature of Federated Learning only aggravates [11]. From the **qualifying** and **onboarding** phases to **integration** to **monitoring**, it permeates the whole FL lifecycle.

Well before onboarding new edge nodes –another hospital, for example– to our network, we should have in place a clear, auditable set of qualifying criteria (e.g. incentive model, hosting capabilities, training resources, available datasets...) that potential candidates are expected to meet in order to officially become nodes. This pre-selection step, though critical to the whole network performance, does not usually get the recognition it deserves, due to either monetary or time constraints.

Immediately after, in the onboarding *per se*, data quality must be assessed again. It also comes into play when using and integrating a **Common Data Model (CDM)**, since training algorithms with datasets from heterogeneous sources –like Electronic Health Records (EHRs)– has a negative impact in network maintenance and scalability, which can only be mitigated by enforcing a single CDM for the central and edge nodes [12]. For GenoMed4All, our CDM pick is FHIR (Fast Health Interoperable Resources), a standard that defines how healthcare data may be exchanged between nodes regardless of how it is actually stored in those nodes. Compared to other standards alternatives, FHIR shows large (and growing) adoption rates among care providers and has

sufficient support for genomic data representation, two key and decisive arguments in the context of GenoMed4All. However, the future healthcare industry seems to be slowing but surely edging towards more fluid scenarios that favor the co-existence of a wide variety of CDM standards – for instance, the emerging OpenEHR standard. This trend would be especially relevant in federated ecosystems like GenoMed4All's, since they intend to amalgamate an ever-growing, wildly heterogenous landscape of hospitals under a unique distributed umbrella.

Monitoring data quality during training is also tricky: every time datasets are added to the network, there is a need to evaluate whether they are really up-to-standard, mainly to avoid entering a new training loop that ultimately pushes back an updated, poorer quality model to the central server.

On top of these sizeable pile of issues to consider lies the unescapable fact that we are operating in the healthcare realm, where challenges in data integration are always multi-faceted. New social determinants –linked to decision support, care pathways, medication...– and unconventional sources of information –social media, the Internet of Things– have started to permeate the way we look at and make sense of healthcare processes ... and in turn, this heightened understanding has exposed a pressing need to outline and regulate data subject rights. As a result, the concept of 'digital sovereignty' has been coined to protect the individual's right for autonomy in a predominantly digital world, and the EU has embraced this notion as the cornerstone of its strategy to usher in a new area of European digital leadership centered around ensuring citizens retain control over their personal data.

Security challenges

In a cross-silo FL scenario, one of the most pressing issues currently under the spotlight is linked to **data and client system security**, or how to prevent information leaks during the multiple update iterations. Even if no data is exchanged between edge nodes and the central server, the model may still contain some patient-sensitive information in its parameters. The server is normally the one exploiting this vulnerability, since it centralizes client updates and has more control on the FL process as a whole. Solutions to this problem rely on Secure Multiparty Computation (SMC) to aggregate updates or Differential Privacy (DP) to distort client updates locally. Additionally, we might need to also protect the central server against potential malicious client attacks from the edge nodes: those aiming to compromise the convergence of the global model by either disrupting the training process or providing false updates [13]. For GenoMed4All this is not as relevant an issue since all partners participating as clients are considered trusted nodes in the network.

Platform challenges

The current landscape of Federated Learning platforms –and their features– paints a picture of highly heterogenous, research-specific and not yet mature alternatives (e.g. [Flower](#), [Fedbiomed](#), [Fate](#), [TensorFlow Federated](#), [PySyft](#), [Paddle](#)) that are emerging as an unequivocal sign of all the excitement and interest surrounding FL. Key platform capabilities like configurability, robustness, scalability, performance, user experience... are non-negotiable for GenoMed4All's ambition. After all, we are working on a production environment that intends to serve an ever-growing community with an increasing number of algorithms and use cases.

But how to make this vision a reality? The problem is, modern workspace software environments are sorely missing a **model federation dimension**. Nowadays, AI platforms are mature enough to handle everything from data exploration, testing, pre-processing and transformation and feature engineering to model validation and deployment... and yet, they still have not figured out how to support a model federation approach. As a result, we are missing out on several fronts: first, on **metadata exploration tools** for data scientists to build their models and features on; and second, on workspaces with **adequate debug, development and testing capabilities** to handle models with

longer lifecycles and incremental contributions from edge nodes [14]. The inevitable conclusion? Team **productivity and efficiency** are greatly impacted.

Another contender for top platform challenge in FL is **data extraction**. Data scientists follow complex workflows for model development and data extraction plays a major role in the selection, (cohort) transformation and feature extraction steps. These operations must be first formalized by the platform so they can then be automatically reproduced on the edge nodes. For data scientists, a platform that can provide easy-to-use tools to step away from manual configuration before jumping to model deployment is certainly a bonus. That is why we are taking care to integrate a flexible ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) tool –containing data cohort definition linked to the target model– to configure data extraction and transformation steps from the CDM to the algorithms in GenoMed4All's platform.

All these challenges are represented in the scorecard below, described in the context of GenoMed4All and ranked in order of priority (i.e. we have marked with 3 stars those that we consider to be core challenges in the project).

The GenoMed4All project or why Federated Learning will serve rare disease research

At GenoMed4All we are building a Federated Learning platform where clinicians and researchers can work together in the definition, development, testing and validation of AI models to improve the way we currently diagnose and treat hematological diseases in the EU. We envision two complementary **operational modes** for this platform: a **clinical** mode, catering to the needs of healthcare professionals and patients in their daily practice; and a **research** mode, where data scientists can train and benchmark AI models from available data on hematological diseases.

For **clinicians**, GenoMed4All's platform will act as a local decision support system to input new prospective and retrospective patient data, extracting insights from an ever-learning model. For **researchers**, GenoMed4All offers an AI sandbox to benchmark and train new AI models on real-world data and to ensure their clinical usability, a critical point that has so far hampered the real-world integration of AI applications in healthcare.

At GenoMed4all, we believe that a radical shift in how we introduce these kind of tools to a clinical setting is sorely needed to ensure their accountability, transparency and usefulness among healthcare professionals. Drawing a parallel to how we rely on solid pharmaco-vigilance processes to monitor adverse reactions and ultimately confirm a certain drug is safe for use, we can certainly envision a similar clinical validation flow for these tools that successfully undergoes the same level of scrutiny and meets the required standards for performance excellence in a clinical setting.

	Clinical mode	Research mode
Main actors / Context	Pre-trained predictive model, clinicians and patients	Retrospective (secondary) data, IT/data specialist from data provider organization, clinical data scientist/researcher
Functionality	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Clinicians extract data during patient visits, possibly also through laboratory tests 2 Clinicians then input individual patient's data into the platform and select a specific predictive algorithm based on the patient's needs 3 The model outputs a prediction on the patient's health status, which is interpreted by clinicians (alongside all other evidence they may have collected on the patient) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Clinical data scientists perform an initial exploration with local data to define the predictive model's architecture and hyperparameters 2 Data providers upload their data to be transformed to our CDM 3 The predictive model is trained on the whole dataset, including local contributions from several different organizations via the FL paradigm 4 The global predictive model can be broadcasted back to the sources and must be tested for generalization capability and absence of bias
Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FL enables clinical data providers to contribute to the training of predictive models while respecting patients' privacy and GDPR regulations 	

All in all, we have seen that Federated Learning is indeed an emerging technology that is still finding its footing within the research field. The cross-silo approach we have followed does provide a number of unquestionably attractive capabilities for AI applications in the clinical research space, namely those in the data privacy domain. However, several challenges lurk in the horizon... and must be addressed before this approach can finally become mainstream practice in the healthcare industry, so that Federated Learning can effectively deliver on all the promises we have navigated through in this miniseries.

In this research space, GenoMed4All plays a pioneer role as it explores the large spectrum of issues raised by Federated Learning in healthcare: from platform technology selection and development all the way to defining the full data flow and Common Data Model, security, privacy and an end-to-end operational model. This close collaboration environment, spearheaded by multiple care providers in Europe, leading edge research institutions and recognized industrial partners (meet our stellar team [here!](#)) is our core strength to pave the way forward and deliver on new innovation opportunities.

Missed anything? Check out these references!

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